

The Impact of the Housing Accelerator Fund on Population in Saskatoon

Muqaiba Imtiaz¹, Scott Bell¹, Olha Khrebtishcheva¹, Ehab Diab¹, Marlo Edwards²

¹Geography and Planning, University of Saskatchewan, muqaiba.imtiaz@usask.ca, scott.bell@usask.ca, olha.khrebtishcheva@usask.ca, ehab.diab@usask.ca

²Communications, Okanagan College, meeedwards@okanagan.bc.ca

ABSTRACT

This study will compare the potential population growth in three zones in Saskatoon, SK. Each zone is associated with Saskatoon's Housing Accelerator Fund (HAF) program: 1. the Corridor Growth Area (CGA) is closest to Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) routes; 2. the Transportation Development Area (TDA) is a larger area still surrounding the BRT route; and 3. the non-HAF area. Our study will examine one corridor that passes through these three zones, Clarence Avenue. "Clarence" is a 4-lane motor vehicle-focused, urban roadway. While it passes through the above three zones, it is not part of the to-be-implemented BRT system. This study reports on a parcel-by-parcel assessment of maximum parcel-level redevelopment and uses 2021 household population and maximum allowed housing to estimate population increases if each zone is fully developed. Our findings demonstrate that Saskatoon's population, along this single roadway, would grow by 1636, and that this growth would happen largely in the two HAF areas, with the region closest to the BRT having the potential to experience a population increase of 83%.

Keywords: densification, Canadian cities, population growth, population projection, housing access, multi-unit development, demographic modelling.

1. Introduction

The Housing Accelerator Fund (HAF) was announced in the 2022 Canadian federal budget. The primary objective of HAF is to increase housing supply across the country. This new housing will simultaneously meet local demand while also supporting environmental sustainability and economic flexibility. Creating more housing will contribute to achieving SDG #11.1, which aims to create access to affordable and safe housing by 2030 (United Nations, 2015). HAF provides funding directly to local governments to incentivize affordable and equitable housing (Government of Canada, 2024). In February 2024, the City of Saskatoon (CoS) submitted its Housing Action proposal to the Government of Canada. It was subsequently accepted, and CoS was allocated \$41.325 million from the Housing Accelerator Fund, distributed over the following three years (City of Saskatoon, 2024) (Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation, 2025). The City of Saskatoon is using the funds to densify housing, particularly along identified transit corridors connecting residents to common destinations. These corridors are aligned with Saskatoon's Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) routes. In particular, the Transit Development Area (TDA) is an 800-meter (a 10-minute walk) area around planned BRT stations and routes (City of Saskatoon, 2025). The Corridor Growth Area (CGA) is a sub-section of the TDA, covering an even shorter distance surrounding BRT routes (fig. 1).

The implementation of HAF and BRT is also tied to equity. BRT routes closely align with the distribution of Indigenous and Metis populations, as well as people of lower socioeconomic status, and immigrant populations (fig. 2) in CoS (Pandey et al., 2023). Concentrating HAF development on the BRT will provide better access to more affordable housing for these populations and contribute to housing equity for populations most in need.

Figure 1. Saskatoon, SK, with HAF regions.

Figure 2. The distribution of immigrants across Saskatoon, SK by dissemination area.

The TDA and CGA both encourage more dense housing. One comparison that will be interesting is with the non-HAF area, since it also enables the “densification” of properties, as was allowed prior to HAF approval. For this reason, our estimate for future growth includes increased population outside the HAF regions where current single-family homes can have laneway suites or basement suites (one of each allowed), or be sub-divided (for parcels 15m or wider). For the two HAF areas, even greater housing density is allowed. Within the TDA, multi-unit dwellings of up to four units are allowed on sites with a minimum width of 21 meters. Additionally, corner lots in the TDA as narrow as 15m are approved for development of up to four units. CoS sees corner lots as important areas for densification (Planning and Development, n.d.). The CGA allows for even higher level of housing density; further broadening the eligibility, which allows multi-unit dwellings on sites with a minimum width of 15 meters; these sites are closest or adjacent to the BRT routes. The 15-meter constraint in the CGA allows for more potential units in the CGA than the TDA. Furthermore, the capacity of lots in the CGA is even greater, as eligible lots (based on dimensions) can hold multi-unit and multi-floor buildings (Planning and Development, 2024).

2. Methods & Data

To study the potential impact of HAF on population within CoS, we used ArcGIS Pro to visualize, count, and compare demographic data from the 2021 census at the dissemination area (DA) and block (DB) level. The 2021 census data will serve as our current population and used as a baseline from which to evaluate potential change. In 2021 we note, and other have noted, a concentration of socioeconomic disadvantage, recent immigrant populations, and First Nations and Metis at the DA level (fig. 2). Our primary investigation will be done at the DB level (fig. 3), giving us the ability to estimate potential population growth on a block-by-block basis. DBs are the smallest units of analysis for which summary, but not detailed, population data is available.

Figure 3. The dissemination blocks, TDA, and CGA in Saskatoon, SK.

2.1 Area of Study

Within our study area (CoS), we chose Clarence Avenue - from College Drive to Circle Drive - as our area of study (fig. 4). We chose this site for the following reasons a) it was long enough to cross the CGA, TDA, and non-HAF zones of the city; and b) for individual DBs, both the left and right sides of the street fell within the same HAF zone (CGA, TDA, and non-HAF). There were other viable streets, but we rejected those in favour of Clarence because it meets both criteria and the sub-regions (CGA, TDA, and non-HAF) were similar in size and number of included DBs. The parcels along Clarence Ave. were classified into the appropriate HAF categories: TDA, CGA, and non-HAF. Population estimates were created based on the maximum number of allowable units in each region. These estimates were based on the aspirational and scenario-based assumption that each property will be redeveloped to the maximum number of housing units under the Saskatoon HAF guidelines (other assumptions, limitations, and opportunities are listed in section 2.3). We started with Saskatoon's average household size according to the 2021 census of 2.5 persons (City of Saskatoon, n.d.).

Figure 4. Area of Study and Units and Analysis: Dissemination Blocks contiguous to Clarence Ave. from College Dr. to Circle Dr., Saskatoon

2.2 TDA and CGA Growth Calculations

In the TDA, current household lots have the potential to hold 4 units. This is also true of the CGA and non-HAF area. For ease of calculation, we assume these lots currently hold a single dwelling (source of some uncertainty). For each region we calculate the maximum number of housing units under the HAF guidelines. For instance, in the TDA to calculate the potential maximum population increase, sites were multiplied by 3 to get the maximum number of units, then multiplied by the average household size to calculate the potential total population.

In the CGA, household lots with 15m (50ft) frontage can be redeveloped without minimum coverage constraints, with multiple units, and multiple storeys (guidelines and policies designate specific heights and number of these storeys) (figs. 5-7, all within 5 blocks of the area of study). Our estimates include all types of development possible under both the TDA and CGA guidelines. Furthermore, we estimate total potential maximum population based on maximally building new housing in the TDA and CGA. In our study area the CGA's 2021 population is approximately the same as the non-HAF zone, whereas the 2021 population for the TDA is higher than the other two; the TDA covers more area – 13 blocks - along Clarence Ave compared to the other two zones, at nine blocks each. Our expectation, or hypothesis, is that the population carrying capacity of the CGA and TDA will be greater than the non-HAF area and will demonstrate the densification possible under HAF guidelines.

Figure 5. Two 15m lots in the TDA pre-HAF development. The property on the left is adjacent to the CGA.

Figure 6. Multi-unit, multi-storey development under construction within the CGA.

Figure 7. A completed multi-unit, multi-storey development within the CGA.

2.3 Assumptions, Limitations, and Opportunities

Growth projections are based on several assumptions. The most apparent is that our application of the HAF development guidelines of all eligible parcels is unrealistic. However, in order to prepare for growth, it is essential that such upper limits of growth be modeled. City, provincial, and other utility services will rely on such estimates to ensure new residential development is appropriately serviced. This means our estimates are maximal theoretical estimates. Such estimates also allow residents to visualize what their city might look like in the future. Furthermore, the same type of analysis could be applied to other jurisdictions in Canada, many of which have also accepted HAF funding. Every jurisdiction accepting HAF funding has similarly updated their master plan to align with the changes they will make. Each of those documents will provide the basis for how population calculations can be estimated based on the local scenarios.

3. Results

The 2021 populations for each area reflect the sizes of the zones. The Non-HAF region and CBA have similar populations and geographic dimensions, while the TDA's is higher: both the non-HAF and CBA regions are nine blocks each, while the TDA is 13 blocks. The number of eligible sites per zone is highest for the CBA, as it has the highest potential for densification (see fig. 6 and 7). The population growth potential for the areas surrounding BRT in CoS is, as we hypothesized, greatest in the CGA (Table 1) (Fig. 8). The government's intention with HAF is to create more and denser housing. Our results indicate that population growth adjacent to the BRT will be highest in the CGA. The CGA experiences a larger increase in estimated population compared to the TDA, due to its planning guidelines allowing more dense development. The CGA's population estimate is an 84% increase while the TDA's population grows by 34.3%, as there are fewer additional units possible since fewer sites are eligible for densification. The non-HAF region surprisingly has a similar estimated growth rate as the TDA; although there are fewer eligible sites, they make up a larger proportion of the non-HAF region than the TDA's. Overall, Clarence Avenue could experience an increase of 49.3% in its total population with an additional 1636 people; an estimated growth rate of approximately half its current population is a definite demonstration of the HAF's densification abilities.

Table 1: Population estimate data for all three regions.

	2021 Population	Number of Eligible Sites	Additional Units Possible	HAF Population Estimate	Population Increase
non-HAF	910	47	141	1263	38.7%
TDA	1489	68	204	1999	34.3%
CBA	920	103	309	1693	84.0%
Totals	3319	218	654	4955	49.3%

Figure 8. The estimated growth of each region and the total estimated growth of Clarence Ave.

4. Discussion & Conclusion

The higher level of densification allowed in the CGA relative to the TDA can be attributed to lower minimum width requirements, site coverage capacity, and allowing multiple floor developments. By assigning a minimum width at 15 meters for the CGA, the city has made it easier for sites within the CGA to qualify for densification. This should also result in a gradient of increasing population density and number of dwellings: with lower potential growth furthest from BRT lines (non-HAF) to greater capacity in BRT-adjacent areas (CGA). As such, we demonstrate the potential future population and housing density will be lowest outside the HAF areas, higher in the TDA, and highest in the CGA (BRT-adjacent).

The Housing Accelerator Fund represents the Canadian government's largest housing intervention and the federal government's first foray into the planning and development of Canada's cities (Pomeroy, 2022). It is primarily intended to address housing shortages, supply, and demand across the country. Allowing local governments to propose their own plans ensures that the housing needs of each community are being met through the HAF and that plans can be implemented in a locally relevant and, hopefully, palatable manner. In Saskatoon, the majority of the \$41.325 million the city received in HAF funding was allocated towards developing denser housing corridors along major arterial roads that coincide with BRT routes. Specifically, our research found that the city's initiative to allow multi-unit dwellings on lots meeting certain width requirements will result in a variation of densification across different sections of Clarence Avenue. This research and methodology can be expanded to all other areas of Saskatoon; furthermore, it can apply to other cities receiving HAF funding.

Future research will address broader issues of access and equity. We acknowledge that the BRT routes are linked to concentrations of lower socioeconomic and marginalized populations across Saskatoon. Those populations have been further connected to poorer access to healthy food (Engler-Stringer et al., 2014) and healthcare (Jones et al., 2016). Future research can examine whether HAF densification impacts the access marginalized populations have to these necessities, and if it can have equalizing effects in regard to socioeconomic factors.

Acknowledgments

This research has funded by the Research Junction (CoS and USask research partnership) and SSHRC. The authors thank the CoS and our direct partners Tyson McShane and Michael Kowalchuk.

References

- Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation. (2025, February 28). *HAF Agreement and Action Plan Summary Saskatoon – Saskatchewan*. <https://assets.cmhc-schl.gc.ca/sites/cmhc/professional/project-funding-and-mortgage-financing/funding-programs/all-funding-programs/housing-accelerator-fund/action-plan-summaries/haf-action-plan-summary-saskatoon-en.pdf?rev=43d1c183-2578-4f6d-9665-d48b345d9ee7>
- City of Saskatoon. (n.d.). *Community Quick Facts* [Fact Sheet]. <https://www.saskatoon.ca/sites/default/files/documents/City%20of%20Saskatoon.pdf>
- City of Saskatoon. (2024). *Housing Accelerator Fund*. Saskatoon City Council. <https://www.saskatoon.ca/HAF>

- City of Saskatoon. (2025). *Housing Action Plan*. City of Saskatoon, Business and Development. <https://www.saskatoon.ca/business-development/planning/programs-projects/housing-action-plan>
- Engler-Stringer, R., Shah, T., Bell, S., Muhajarine, N. (2014, October). *Geographic access to healthy and unhealthy food sources for children in neighbourhoods and from elementary schools in a mid-sized Canadian city*. *Spatial and Spatio-temporal Epidemiology*, 11, 23-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sste.2014.07.001>
- Government of Canada. (2024). *Housing Accelerator Fund*. Infrastructure Canada. https://housing-infrastructure.canada.ca/pd-dp/parl/2024/02/fina/fina-a-eng.html#toc_6
- Jones, M., Shah, T., Hayes, A., Uswak, G., & Bell, S. (2016). *Dental service disparities in Canada: A Saskatoon, Saskatchewan case study*. *The Canadian Geographer/Le Géographe canadien*, 60(3), 346-355. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3088.7524>
- Pandey, U.N., Bell, S., Diab, E., Fuller, D., Stephens, Z.P. (2023). Local Access to Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) in Saskatoon, SK: An Equity Assessment. *Spatial Knowledge and Information Canada*. https://skiconference.ca/2023/papers/SKI2023_paper_15.pdf
- Planning and Development. (2024, May 17). *Housing Accelerator Fund – Four Storey Development within the Transit Development Area* [Fact sheet]. City of Saskatoon. <https://www.saskatoon.ca/sites/default/files/documents/community-services/planning-development/4%20Storey%20FAQ%20-%202024.05.17.pdf>
- Planning and Development. (n.d.) *Housing Accelerator Fund – Permitting 4 Dwelling Units per Site* [Fact sheet]. City of Saskatoon. <https://www.saskatoon.ca/sites/default/files/documents/community-services/planning-development/4%20Units%20FAQ.pdf>
- Pomeroy, S. (2022, January). *Observations and Suggestions for the Proposed Housing Accelerator Fund*. Canadian Housing Evidence Collaborative (CHEC). <https://chec-ccrl.ca/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Observations-and-suggestions-for-the-Housing-Accelerator-Fund-Jan-30.pdf>
- United Nations. (2015). *Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable*. U.N. Department of Economic and Social Affairs. https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11#targets_and_indicators